

The Effects of Modifications on the Functional Characteristics of Native and Chemically Modified Starches Isolated from Two *Digitaria* Varieties

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Tetfund Sponsored Institutional Based Research (IBR)

ABSTRACT

Starch, the most abundant carbohydrate in nature has various industrial and domestic applications and is extracted from main sources like grains and tubers. Native starch has limited applications due to low shear resistance, thermal decomposition and retrogradation that necessitate modifications. Obtaining starch from common sources leads to competitive demand which necessitated sourcing starch among underutilised crops such as *Digitaria exilis* (De) and *Digitaria iburua* (Di). Therefore, the aim of this study was to extract starches from De and Di, modify the starches and determine their physicochemical and functional properties.

The yields of starch in De and Di were 88.0% and 76.1%, respectively. Moisture, ash, fat and protein contents of De and Di native and modified starches ranged from 8.4-13.5%; 0.6-1.2%; 0.1-0.4% and 0.3-1.1%, respectively. Increase in temperature improved the swelling power and solubility by 6.0-7.0% and 2.0-3.1%, respectively, with highest swelling in oxidised De (13.0g/g) and Di (13.1g/g), and highest solubility in acetylated De (10.1g/g) and Di (10.1g/g). Native and modified starches formed gel at concentration $\geq 12.0\%$ for all the samples. The WAC decreased in all the modified starches (0.4-0.8g/g) when compared to the native (1.0g/g), and the highest WAC was observed in oxidised De (0.8g/g) and Di (0.8g/g). Amylose content present in native and modified starches ranged from 20.7-26.1%. The native starches had the lowest pasting temperature at 77.0 °C, while the acetylated starches had the highest at 91.3 °C, indicating reorientation of starch granules chains. The final viscosity decreased with chemical modifications with a range of 1957-3458, 1334-1398 and 604-608 RVU for acetylation, oxidation and acid-thinning, against 4215-4720 RVU for native De and Di, respectively.

Chemical modifications improved the swelling power, solubility, gelation capacity and water absorption capacity of *Digitaria exilis* and *Digitaria iburua* starches, affording them potential for industrial applications.

Keywords: *Digitaria* varieties, Acetylated starches, Starch oxidation, Acid-thinning, underutilised.

1 Introduction

Starch is the homopolysaccharide, which is stored as a food material in plants, the largest prevalent organic compound (Haq et al., 2019). It is found in leaves, flowers, fruits, seeds, different types of stems and roots. Starch is used by plants as source of carbon and energy (Smith, 2001). The biochemical chain responsible for starch synthesis involves glucose molecules produced in plant cells by photosynthesis. It is the polymeric form of anhydrous glucose units, which are generally setup in the unique and autonomous granules (Haq et al., 2019). Starch is a semi-crystalline biopolymer, which is constituted of linear amylose and branched amylopectin molecule where the linear chain of amylose comprised of α -(1-4)-linked D-glucose units and the amylopectin contains smaller chains of α -(1-4)-linked D-glucan having branches at α -(1-6)-linked D-glucose linkages (Verma and Srivastav, 2022).

Starch is well known for its biocompatibility, biodegradability, low cost and nontoxicity (Qiao *et al.*, 2016; Liu *et al.*, 2015; Mahmoudian *et al.*, 2012). However, native starch has limited applications due to its insolubility in water even at 25°C and gentle regress so, starch is modified either chemically, physically or genetically (Smith, 2001) in order to make it more useful and to enhance its application. Even though starch is extensively used in the native form, it is also being employed in versatile starch-based food products due to its different properties. Chemical modifications usually lead to an increase in film formation, freeze-thaw stability, adhesion, and emulsifying properties, and a decrease in retrogradation, paste or gel syneresis, and paste gelling tendency of the rice starch (Bao and Bergman 2004). The modified starches have been used in many food products; for example, they are utilised to decrease the stickiness of starchy foods and to act as dough conditioners and crumb softeners in bread, thereby retarding staling in these products (Copeland et al. 2009). Starch has been chemically modified to enhance gelatinisation, enhance cooking properties, and inhibit retrogradation and gelling tendencies (Morikawa and Nishirani, 2008). Alkali treatment, oxidation or bleaching, partial enzymatic hydrolysis, and partial acid hydrolysis are examples of chemical conversion of starch. Dual modification, etherification, esterification and cross-linking, are examples of chemical modification through derivatisation. Acetylation and oxidation are two common chemical modifications; oxidised starches are used extensively in sectors such as paper, where they improve the robustness and printability. It was also useful in the textile, laundry finishing, construction, and culinary sectors (Lawal *et al.*, 2005).

Based upon great demands on starch with more attention primarily on stable foods, it has become necessary to explore underutilized crops of the small-sized fonio of the genus, *Digitaria spp*, a traditional cereal grown in Western Africa (Ayanan *et al.*, 2018). Compared with major cereals, such as wheat and rice, fonio is a type of underutilized cereal grains with potential for food applications (Mbosso *et al.*, 2020). There are two types of fonio grains, including white fonio (*Digitaria exilis*) (commonly called acha, fundi, or hungry rice) and black fonio (*Digitaria iburua*) (commonly called iburu) (Odeku, 2013). Both cereals have high digestible energy content but a low mineral and fat content. They might be transformed into a range of foods, including gruels, porridges, drinks and so on and are either eaten whole or ground into flour (Coda *et al.*, 2010).

Fonio has attracted attention from some other parts of the world for food applications (Abrouk et al., 2020; Jideani, 2012; Laheri, and Soon, 2018). For example, fonio is being actively and commercially promoted in the United States as a “healthy” grain (Roseboro, 2020). European Union has recently approved fonio as a novel food (European Commission, 2018). Hence, the aim of this research therefore

was to isolate starch from the two samples, compare their physicochemical characteristics, modify and characterise starches obtained from fonio white (*Digitaria exilis*) and fonio black (*Digitaria iburua*)

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Sample Collection

The two varieties (*Digitaria exilis Stapf*) and (*Digitaria iburua Stapf*) were bought at Minna Central Market, Minna, Nigeria. The stones and all unwanted materials were removed. Every reagent that was employed was of analytical grade.

2.2 Starch Extraction

One kg each of the samples was immersed in a 0.3% sodium hydroxide solution of 10 L distilled water at 25°C for 24 hours and the pH adjusted to 8.0. After that, it was manually swirled for half an hour. The steep liquor was drained off; pigment was removed by washing them in distilled water and ground for 30 minutes at 200 r.p.m. using warring blend (Warring Commercial Torrington Connecticut 0670 Model, 24CB10, America). The resulting slurry from the blending process was again suspended in a 0.3% sodium hydroxide solution of 10 L distilled water, manually agitated for 20 minutes and waited 6 hours to settle and the supernatant was removed by draining. Until the supernatant produced a negative result for the protein test (Biuret), this procedure was repeated. Distilled water was used to suspend the slurry; after using 0.5 M HCl to raise the pH to 7.0, the mixture was run through a nylon screen (80 µm). The clear supernatant was then disposed of after it had settled for an additional six hours, and washed four times using distilled water (Lawal *et al.*, 2011). Drying was done on the starch that was isolated for 72 hours at (30 ± 2°C) room temperature, stored and labeled in polythene bags until used. The proximate compositions of the starches were determined accordingly by official methods of analysis described by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists, 2010 edition.

2.3 Chemical modification of the starches

The chemical modifications processes employed for this research were namely oxidation, acid thinning and acetylation.

2.3.1 Starch oxidation

The process of Autio *et al.* (1996) using slight changes as carried out by Dias *et al.* (2011) was engaged. A 40% starch slurry was prepared using a heating mantle in a 2 L reaction vessel attached. The slurry of starch stayed at 35°C by periodically shutting down the mantle, and 2 M NaOH was used to get the pH down to 9. Sodium hypochlorite, 60 g (0.8 g NaOCl / 100 g starch, 0.8% w/w) was gradually added to the starch slurry while using 2 M H₂SO₄ to keep the pH at 9.5. Following the inclusion of sodium hypochlorite, the slurry's pH was kept at 9.5 for an extra 50 minutes using 2 M sodium hydroxide. The sludge was subsequently adjusted with 2 M H₂SO₄ filtered to pH 7.0 using a vacuum (whatman paper), cleaned using de-ionized water and oven-dried at 40°C for 48 hours.

2.3.2 Starch Acid Thinning

The process of Chen *et al.* (2015) was utilised in order to prepare of acid thinned starch of *D. Exilis* and *D. Iburua*. A 200 g on a dry basis of starch samples was suspended in 6% (w/v) HCl in 600 mL to hydrolyse it. At 50°C for 24 hours, solution was left in a heated plate or water bath and throughout the course of treatment, the slurry was constantly agitated. Using a 10% (w/v) solution of NaOH, the reaction was neutralised at the conclusion of the reaction time to stop it. After that, the suspension was repeatedly rinsed with distilled water three times until the filtrate was clear of the corresponding ions. The moist acid treated starch was allowed to air dry for 48 hours at 30°C ± 2.0°C. In order to acquire powdered starch treated by acid, and lastly, the dry powder was sieved using a 100-mesh sifter.

2.3.3 Starch Acetylation

Acetylation of starch samples were made using Van Hung and Morita's (2005) methodology, but with a few minor modifications as employed by Ashogbon and Akintayo (2014). A 500 mL of distilled water were mixed with 100 grams of starch; for 20 minutes, it was swirled magnetically. A 1.0 M NaOH was added to the resulting slurry to bring its pH down to 8.0. During the course of an hour, acetic anhydride weighing 10.2 g was added while keeping the pH between 8.0 and 8.5. After the addition of acetic anhydride, the reaction persisted for five minutes. With the use of 0.5 M HCl, the slurry's pH was brought to 4.5. The content was sifted, cleaned with distilled water four times, then allow to air dry at 30°C ± 2.0°C for 48 hours.

2.4 Physicochemical Parameters

2.4.1 Effect of Temperature on Swelling and Solubility

The starches' solubility and swelling power were ascertained by a process adapted by Vanier *et al.* (2012). A 500 mg starch sample was measured and put in a centrifuge tube (W_1). Next, 20 mL of water was used to dissolve the starch. It was at that point placed in a thermostated water bath and heated for 30 minutes at different temperatures between 65°C and 95°C. Following a cooling period to ambient temperature, the mixture was agitated for 15 minutes at 3000 g. To calculate the swelling power, the supernatant was cautiously poured off and the residue weighed. The dry centrifuge tube's weight, together with the residue and water it held, were calculated as W_2 . The swelling power was calculated using equation.

$$\% \text{ Swelling power} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{\text{Weight of Starch}}$$

A 5 mL supernatant was aliquotted and dried at 110°C until it reached a consistent weight. The amount of starch soluble in water was indicated by the residue left over after the supernatant was dried. On a dry weight basis, g per 100 g of starch was used to calculate solubility (Adebowale *et al.*, 2009).

2.4.2 Water and Oil Absorption Capacity of Starches

The Arawande and Borokini process (2010) but with a small adjustment as performed by Ibeabuchi *et al.* (2017) was employed to test the starch's ability to absorb water and oil. One gram of starch was

combined with 10 mL of clean oil or water (Kings vegetable oil) for 30 seconds. A mixer was used to combine the suspension for 30 seconds, let to stand at room temperature for half an hour before being centrifuged for 30 minutes at 5000 rpm. The volume was measured after the supernatant was decanted into a measuring cylinder. Based on dry weight, the mass of water or oil absorbed was represented as g/g starch.

$$WAC \text{ or } OAC (\%) = \frac{\text{Volume of bound water or oil}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100\%$$

2.4.3 Determination of Amylose of Starches

The colorimetric method identified the amount of amylose present in the samples using iodine however with further modifications as suggested by Hoover and Ratnayake (2001) and employed by Li *et al.* (2020). A 1 g of flour was weighed into a 100 mL volumetric flask, and 1 mL of 95% ethanol was then added to moisten it. The mixture was left at room temperature during the night after 10 mL of 0.5 M KOH was added. After being diluted to 100 mL with distilled water, the combination was once more kept overnight at room temperature. After pipetting a 5 mL aliquot of the diluted solution from the mixture into an additional 100 mL volumetric flask, three drops of 0.1% phenolphthalein solution were added to it. Until a neutral pH was reached, the resultant solution was neutralised dropwise with 1M HCl. The neutralised solution was then filled to capacity with distilled water and supplemented with 2 mL of a 0.2% iodine solution in 2% KI.

Using a 100 ppm stock amylose solution, standard solutions of amylose in the range of 0–10 ppm were made and handled similarly like sample above. On a Spectronic 21D Spectrophotometer, the absorbance or optical density of the sample and reference solutions of varying concentration range were measured 30 minutes after the addition of 0.2% iodine solution at a wavelength of 630 nm.

% Amylose was computed with the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Amylose} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample} \times \text{gradient factor} \times \text{dilution factor}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100\%$$

2.4.4 Effect of Concentration on Gelation of Starches

The starches' gelation characteristics were calculated using the methodology of Adebowale *et al.* (2009). Test tubes were filled with 5 mL of distilled water to create precise starch suspensions of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, and 20% (w/v). The test tubes holding these suspensions were then quickly cooled under flowing cold tap water after an hour of heating at 80°C in a water bath. Test tubes were placed in a cooling environment even more to 4°C for 2 hours. The concentration at which, when the test tube was filled, the sample could not slide or fall when turned upside down was identified as the least gelation concentration.

2.4.5 Pasting Properties of Starches

A Rapid Visco Analyser was used for the pasting characteristics of native and modified starches. A 3.5 g (dry basis) of starches were mixed with 25 mL of distilled water that was kept in a canister. The paddle was put into the canister, positioned in the center and inserted into the RVA machine after the paddle coupling. By pressing the instrument's motor tower, the measurement cycle was started. On the computer's display linked to the instrument, the profile can be viewed in action. At a constant shear rate, an automated cycle of heating and cooling was utilised. The time-temperature regime employed was 50°C for one minute of idle, followed by 3 minutes and 45 seconds of heating to 95°C, and finally 2 minutes and 30 seconds of holding at 95°C. The 13-minute profile was utilised. After that, the sample was cooled to 50°C over the course of two minutes and forty-five seconds. After that, the temperature was maintained at 50°C for another two minutes. The parameters of pasting, such as peak viscosity, time to peak, temperature at peak, hot pasting viscosity breakdown, and pasting temperature, final viscosity as well as setback values were then recorded (Lawal *et al.*, 2011).

2.5 Statistical Analysis

The analyses were performed in triplicate and expressed as means \pm standard deviation of measurements. The statistical evaluations of significant differences were performed using Turkey's test at level of significance ($p \leq 0.05$).

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Proximate Composition

Table 1 showed the percentage of the isolated starches from the seed grains of the two samples as well as the proximate composition of native and chemically modified *D. exilis* and *D. iburua* starches. The yields of starches isolated were 88.01% and 76.07% for *D. exilis* and *D. iburua* respectively. These were more than the result of Arueya and Oyewale (2015) that reported a starch content of *D. exilis* to be 75.5%. This variation in the starch content could be related to the maturity stage, different climatic and agronomic conditions. Also, these results were much higher than % starch available in some conventional sources as reported by Sandhu *et al.* (2007) where 72-74% starch was found in maize, 68% in sorghum, 25% in cassava and Adebawale *et al.* (2009) reported 51-67% starch in African Yam Bean.

The moisture content of starches of both native and chemically modified two *Digitaria spp.* ranged from 8.36% to 13.54%. Each sample had slightly varying moisture content from each other. It could be seen from the results that moisture content of native starches of *D. exilis* and *D. iburua* compared with the chemically modified starches were much greater. This could be related to the drying time and temperature when modification was taking place (Ahmed *et al.*, 2013). Following modification, the acetylated starches of *D. exilis* and *D. iburua* were observed to have reduced moisture content values

while the oxidised and acid thinned starches moisture contents levels increased gradually. The results of the proximate composition of both the native and modified starches as presented in this table showed the moisture content of native *D. exilis* and *D. iburua* to range between 12.62 to 13.54% with *D. iburua* having higher moisture content. While that of the modified starches ranged from 8.36 to 9.80%. The moisture content of both the native and modified starches is within the acceptable range that could enhance a long storage time and shelf life of the starches.

The crude fat contents of the oxidised starches were 0.48% and 0.55% while acetylated starches were 0.57% and 0.63% for both *D. exilis* and *D. iburua*, which were low when compared to acid thinned starches of 0.67% and 0.76% with native starches of the two samples 0.83% and 0.90% respectively. Meanwhile, the crude fat contents of the chemically modified and natural starches were the lowest as presented in this table. Modified starches with low fat and moisture contents are essential for long-term preservation, while excessive moisture content levels encourage microbial development and turn the starch discoloured, especially if it surpasses 18% moisture (Gulia, 2014). The crude fibre contents of *D. exilis* of both native and chemically modified starches were lower than in *D. iburua*; the values fell within range of 0.48% - 0.83% and 0.55% - 0.90% respectively. This reduction in the fibre content after the modifications conformed to the findings of the report of Olayinka *et al.* (2013). Additionally, the ash and crude protein contents of the native and modified *D. exilis* were lower to native and modified *D. iburua* which means *D. iburua* has a slight increase in the amounts of non-starch components existing in its native and chemically modified starches. These findings agreed to the observations of Olu- Owolabi *et al.* (2014). The purity of the starches was demonstrated by low amounts of ash and nitrogen in the low values (Sodhi and Singh, 2005). There was a decrease in the amounts of protein, ash, fiber and fat of the chemically modified starches of the two samples after all forms of modification; these low values are suggestive that the samples are free of contaminants.

The large amounts of carbohydrate (>60%) indicated that the starch content of the native starches were high. However, the three modification processes employed i. e. oxidation; acetylation and acid thinning resulted in reduced values for non-starch elements such as moisture content, protein, ash, fat, and fiber; thereby increasing the carbohydrate contents of the chemically modified starches. There was low levels of non-starch constituents in the starches in the two samples though the values in *D. iburua* was a bit higher but with no much difference from *D. exilis*. This positions them helpful in the creation of syrups that contain more glucose than natural starches, and their low protein level makes them suitable in some industrial applications. Degradation of starch molecule following changes may be the cause of reductions in fat, fiber, protein, and % ash stated. The results obtained for the proximate composition of the starches are consistent with the report that wet milling process produce starch with higher purity compared to dry milling process (Hoover *et al.*, 2010).

Table 1: Proximate Composition of Native and Modified *Digitaria spp* Starches (on Dry Basis)

Sample	Yield %	Moisture %	Protein %	Crude Fibre %	Crude Fat %	Ash %	Carbohydrate %
NA	88.01	12.62±0.05 ^d	0.92±0.00 ^b	0.83±0.04 ^b	0.34±0.02 ^a	1.15±0.01 ^c	4.13±0.08 ^e
NI	76.07	13.54±0.03 ^d	1.12±0.08 ^c	0.90±0.02 ^b	0.40±0.02 ^a	1.17±0.02 ^c	82.87±0.10 ^e
OA	-	8.55±0.04 ^e	0.27±0.01 ^b	0.48±0.02 ^c	0.12±0.03 ^a	0.95±0.03 ^d	89.63±0.05 ^f
OI	-	8.48±0.03 ^e	0.38±0.03 ^b	0.55±0.02 ^c	0.19±0.02 ^a	1.07±0.02 ^d	89.32±0.04 ^f
AcA	-	8.39±0.05 ^d	0.57±0.01 ^b	0.57±0.03 ^b	0.20±0.02 ^a	0.83±0.02 ^c	89.45±0.09 ^e
AcI	-	8.36±0.03 ^d	0.70±0.04 ^b	0.63±0.02 ^b	0.25±0.01 ^a	0.93±0.02 ^c	89.12±0.05 ^e
ATA	-	9.59±0.03 ^c	0.63±0.00 ^b	0.67±0.01 ^b	0.28±0.00 ^a	0.63±0.04 ^b	88.20±0.05 ^d
ATI	-	9.80±0.03 ^d	0.85±0.12 ^c	0.76±0.02 ^b	0.33±0.02 ^a	0.64±0.02 ^b	87.60±0.14 ^e

The means of the triple determinations are the results.

NA: Native Acha Starch; NI: Native Iburu Starch; OA: Oxidised Acha Starch; AcA: Acetylated Acha Starch; ATA: Acid Thinned Acha Starch; OI: Oxidised Iburu Starch; AcI: Acetylated Iburu Starch; ATI: Acid Thinned Iburu Starch.

3.2 Effect of Temperature on Swelling power and Solubility of the Native and Modified Starches

Temperature's impact on swelling power and solubility of chemically modified and natural starches are presented in Table 2. Under certain circumstances, the starch's expanding power reveals its capacity to hydrate. The kind of starch is used to determine how much of it is soluble and to what extent and its smaller constituents such as lipids and proteins; nonetheless, starch's swelling power rises with temperature (Adebowale *et al.*, 2002). It has been suggested that swelling power is influenced by bonding forces inside starch granules. As a result, granules of densely linked starch with a large and tightly bound micellar structure ought to be comparatively more resistant to swelling (Wang *et al.*, 2016).

The growing strength of both natural and chemically modified *D. exilis* and *D. iburua* starches was observed to be temperature dependent. Native and modified starches exhibited an increase in swelling power with temperature; this could be explained by the high temperature-induced distraction of starch granules, which then releases all of the amylose from the amylopectin network (Moita *et al.*, 2008). This outcome also concurred with the findings of Olu-Owolabi *et al.* (2014), which indicated that swelling power of native, benzyl and succinyl *D. exilis* grain starches increased with increase in temperature.

There was substantially high swelling power between 75°C to 95°C for all the modified starches, this increase was consistent with observations by other researchers (Van Hung and Morita, 2005; Shon and

Yoo, 2006). The swelling power was a bit higher in oxidized *D. exilis* and *D. iburua* (this was within the range 11.20 – 13.11 g/g) when compared to their corresponding acetylated starches (11.77 – 12.31 g/g). This suggests that acetylation reduced the capability of swelling while oxidation raised it. The increase possibly as a result of the reduction of the binding forces that are seen inside the starch granule, which provided fewer limitations to the modified starches swell, the swelling power on chemical modification, was observed. The result presented in Table 2 revealed that the solubility of native *D. exilis* and *D. iburua* was decreased by all types of modification except in acid thinned starch, though higher values in the solubility of *Iburua* to *Exilis* samples were observed. This observation was in conformity with the reports of Olu-Owolabi *et al.* (2014) and Wang *et al.* (2014).

Sample	Swelling (g/g)				Solubility (g/100g)			
	65°C	75°C	85°C	95°C	65°C	75°C	85°C	95°C
NA	11.66±0.01	11.97±0.01	12.07±0.02	12.37±0.03	10.31±0.03	10.43±0.02	10.75±0.03	10.13±0.03
NI	11.73±0.02	12.05±0.03	12.14±0.02	12.45±0.03	10.34±0.02	10.46±0.01	10.78±0.02	10.16±0.02
OA	11.20±0.03	12.56±0.01	12.97±0.01	13.03±0.02	9.10±0.03	9.26±0.02	9.53±0.02	9.55±0.02
OI	11.23±0.02	12.61±0.03	13.06±0.02	13.11±0.02	9.12±0.01	9.27±0.03	9.55±0.02	9.57±0.03
AcA	11.77±0.02	12.10±0.02	12.26±0.01	12.71±0.04	9.73±0.02	9.70±0.02	9.84±0.02	10.11±0.02
AcI	11.86±0.02	12.17±0.02	12.31±0.03	12.75±0.02	9.75±0.02	9.78±0.02	9.87±0.02	10.13±0.03
ATA	2.17±0.02	2.21±0.04	2.46±0.02	2.51±0.04	11.29±0.03	11.41±0.02	11.71±0.03	10.80±0.03
ATI	2.21±0.03	2.27±0.02	2.51±0.03	2.56±0.02	11.32±0.01	11.44±0.01	11.74±0.03	11.81±0.02

Table 2: Effect of Temperature on Swelling Power (g/g) and Solubility (g/100g) of Native and Chemically Modified *Digitaria* spp. Starches (on dry basis).

The means of the triple determinations are the results.

NA: Native Acha Starch; NI: Native Iburu Starch; OA: Oxidised Acha Starch; AcA: Acetylated Acha Starch; ATA: Acid Thinned Acha Starch; OI: Oxidised Iburu Starch; AcI: Acetylated Iburu Starch; ATI: Acid Thinned Iburu Starch.

3.3 Water and Oil Absorption Capacities of the Native and Modified Starches

Oil and water capabilities of both native and modified *D. exilis* and *D. iburua* starches are shown in Table 3. This table showed that there was a decline of water absorption capacity (WAC) and oil absorption capacity (OAC) in the values of both native and modified starches when compared to the reports of Adebowale *et al.* (2002) where the water and oil absorption capacity were 2.40 and 3.04 g/g respectively; but is in conformity with the report of Olu-Owolabi *et al.* (2014) which showed that acetylation do not increase the capacity to absorb water and oil. The capacity to absorb water reduced in all the modified starches when compared with the native and the ability of starch to absorb water is an indication of its stability in moisture most especially in the food industry, while oil absorption capacity of starch reveals its emulsifying potentials (Adebowale *et al.*, 2006). However, capabilities to absorb water and oil remained relatively constant in all the modified samples as being shown in the table 4 and this was in agreement with Lawal *et al.* (2005). Meanwhile, since both hydrophilic and hydrophobic characteristics decreased after modifications, this could be the result of a rise in the crystallinity of starch, which likely prevented water and oil from entering the grains of starch. Enhanced ability to absorb water is associated with the addition of hydrophilic groups during modification or the decrease in the hydrophobic inclination of the original starch (Gani *et al.*, 2013). Acid thinning reduced the water and oil

absorption capacity of both the *D. exilis* and *D. iburua* starches which is in consistency with the result Reddy *et al.* (2015) that reported acid thinning decreased water absorption capacity. Granular size distribution, crystalline and amorphous areas, and molecular structure of the starch all affect its ability to absorb water.

Table 3: Water and Oil Absorption Capacities of Native and Chemically Modified *Digitaria spp.* Starches (g/g).

Parameter	NA	NI	OA	OI	AcA	AcI	ATA	ATI
WAC	0.99±0.02 ^d	0.99±0.02 ^d	0.81±0.02 ^c	0.81±0.01 ^c	0.63±0.01 ^b	0.63±0.02 ^b	0.38±0.03 ^a	0.38±0.00 ^a
OAC	1.24±0.02 ^{bcd}	1.28±0.01 ^d	1.27±0.01 ^{cd}	1.30±0.01 ^d	1.17±0.01 ^{ab}	1.20±0.02 ^{abc}	1.13±0.01 ^a	1.12±0.02 ^a

The means of the triple determinations are the results.

NA: Native Acha Starch; NI: Native Iburu Starch; OA: Oxidised Acha Starch; AcA: Acetylated Acha Starch; ATA: Acid Thinned Acha Starch; OI: Oxidised Iburu Starch; AcI: Acetylated Iburu Starch; ATI: Acid Thinned Iburu Starch.

3.4 Amylose Content of the Native and Modified Starches

The amylose content significantly influences the functional characteristics of starches because it affects how the crystalline lamella inside starch granules is arranged and how amylopectin is packed into crystallites (Adebowale and Lawal, 2003b). As shown in Table 4, *D. iburua* native starch had the higher value (25.69%) against *D. exilis* native starch with acetylated starch having the highest values and acid thinned lowest (20.71%). Research has indicated that the amylose level of starch differs based on the botanical source and is influenced by soil and climate conditions during grain development (Ashogbon and Akintayo, 2014). The amylose content available in the two samples were within the range of 20-35% known for normal amylose and this finding was in consistent with the reports of Gujral *et al.* (2013) that reported 21.0 to 28.3% in regard to barley starches, nevertheless contradicted the findings of Ali *et al.* (2016) where 4.90 to 8.09% of amylose were gotten from Jhelum and Kohsar rice and corn's starches. Amylose during modification is mostly accessible than amylopectin side chains. Therefore, amylose content is changing due to modification and structural difference between amylose and amylopectin is considered to be the most important factor for starch property. Conclusively, acid thinned starches had the lowest values which agreed with the reports of Sandhu *et al.* (2007) that acid thinning decreases amylose content.

Table 4: Amylose content of both the native and chemically modified starches (%)

Parameters	NA	NI	OA	OI	AcA	AcI	ATA	ATI
Amylose	25.63±0.01 ^c	25.69±0.03 ^c	21.35±0.02 ^b	21.38±0.01 ^b	26.05±0.02 ^d	26.09±0.03 ^d	20.71±0.03 ^a	20.73±0.00 ^a

The means are the triple determinations of the results.

NA: Native Acha Starch; NI: Native Iburu Starch; OA: Oxidised Acha Starch; AcA: Acetylated Acha Starch; ATA: Acid Thinned Acha Starch; OI: Oxidised Iburu Starch; AcI: Acetylated Iburu Starch; ATI: Acid Thinned Iburu Starch.

3.5 Gelation Properties of the Native and Modified Starches

The starches' characteristics during gelation are displayed in Table 5. The gelation index was calculated using the least gelation concentration (LGC). Gelatinisation is a step in the intricate process of starch gel formation; i.e. loss of polarisation when cooked in excess water to increasingly higher temperatures, cross links and permanent swelling of the starch granule occur (Majzoobi and Farahnaky, 2021). It thereby leads to creation of a three-dimensional network through water absorption that provides structural stiffness in a variety of food applications. Gelation properties are affected by the physical rivalry between carbohydrate gelatinisation and protein gelation for water (Abegunde *et al.*, 2013).

The lowest concentration for both samples agreed with the submission of Olu-Owolabi *et al.* (2011, 2014) respectively. However, the observation was different from the findings from Adebowale *et al.* (2009) for native African yam bean which had LGC of 8%. Modifications of *D. exilis* and *D. iburua* improved gel strength over the unmodified starch. Improvement in the gelation properties of the modified could be the result of the decreased protein content giving a better chance to the starch granules to hydrate and form gel easily.

Acid thinning reduced the least gelation concentration of the starches. Acid hydrolysis results in the breakage of the amylose chains gradually decreasing their length. However, depending on the conditions of the reaction, most of the amylose can be degraded thereby affecting the formation, strength, thermo-reversibility and colour of the gel (Amaya-Llano *et al.*, 2008). These authors' explanation could be attributed to the fact that acid breaks amylose chains and progressively decrease their length during acid hydrolysis. Hence, most of the amylose can be degraded depending on hydrolysis conditions thereby affecting the formation, strength, thermo-reversibility and colour of the gel formed.

On the other hand, oxidation and acetylation improved gelation property of the starches; this implies that they are a better gelating food material than the acid thinned starches.

Table 5: Gelation Capacities of both the Native and Chemically Modified Starches (% w/v)

Conc	Remark	NA	NI	OA	OI	AcA	AcI	ATA	ATI
2	Gelation State	Viscous -	Viscous -	Viscous -	Viscous -	Viscous -	Viscous -	Viscous -	Viscous -
4	Gelation State	Viscous -	Viscous -	Viscous -	Viscous -	Viscous -	Viscous -	Viscous -	Viscous -
6	Gelation State	Gel +	Firm gel +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	V -	V -
8	Gelation State	Gel +	Firm gel +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	V -	V -
10	Gelation State	Gel +	Firm gel +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	V -	V -
12	Gelation State	Firm gel +	Firm gel +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	V -	V -
14	Gelation State	Gel +	Firm gel +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +
16	Gelation State	Gel +	Firm gel +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +
18	Gelation State	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +
20	Gelation State	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +	VFG +
LGC		5.92±0.03	6.13±0.02	6.09±0.03	6.21±0.04	6.05±0.02	6.10±0.01	15.81±0.03	15.91±0.04

The means are the triple determinations of the results.

(+) gelation; (-) no gelation; V: viscosity; VFG: very firm gel; LGC: least gelation concentration.

NA: Native Acha Starch; NI: Native Iburu Starch; OA: Oxidised Acha Starch; OI: Oxidised Iburu Starch; AcA: Acetylated Acha Starch; AcI: Acetylated Iburu Starch; ATA: Acid Thinned Acha Starch; ATI: Acid Thinned Iburu Starch.

3.6 Pasting Characteristics of the Native and Modified Starches

The pasting characteristics of native and modified *Digitaria spp.* starches are displayed in Table 4.6. Peak viscosity (Pv) is a crucial characteristic that sets a starch apart at any concentration while the point at which starch starts to thicken is called the pasting temperature. Generally, most changed samples had pasting viscosities ranged from 607 to 3657 RVU that were lower than those of the original samples (4624 to 4639 RVU). Meanwhile, the *D. iburua* native starch had a peak viscosity that was a bit higher than *D. exilis* native starch in contrast to the lower values out of all the modified starches, the more elevated values of the native starches could be ascribed to the starch's unrestrained swelling since there are no functional groups to replace it. The reduction in peak viscosity afterwards oxidation, acetylation and acid thinning agreed to the findings of Atichokudomchai *et al.* (2001) and Adebowale *et al.* (2002) respectively. The viscosity being reduced subsequent to modification processes may be explained by a partial glycosidic bond cleavage, most especially via oxidation; this is as a result of starch molecules' molecular weight decreasing. A reduced viscosity was created by the broken starch because it was not shear resistant and could not preserve the starch granule's structure intact (Lawal *et al.*, 2005). The peak viscosity significantly decreased in acetylated *Exilis* starches against *Iburua* sample while a slight decrease was observed in the native and oxidised *Exilis* starches and *Iburua*.

In a similar manner, following modification, setback and breakdown values were greatly decreased from 1052 to 3 cP and 1397 to 3 cP respectively. Shear thinning of starch is indicated by the breakdown induced via the degradation within the framework of the gelatinised grains of starch while constantly swirling and heating (Ratnayake and Jackson, 2008). Acid thinned starch had the minimum setback value which is followed by oxidised starch with an increase in acetylated and native starches. This observation about the native and modified starches could be attributed to partial dissolution of polymers that took place during the modification operations, or it might be because starch chains are inhibited by functional groups present from joining (Vatanasuchart *et al.*, 2005). Setback value is a gauge of the propensity for starch degradation and the native starch setback value was considerably decreased by chemical changes due to the introduction of the functional groups which lessens the binding forces, which explains decreased viscosity values.

Table 6: RVA Pasting Properties of both the Native and Modified Starches

Sample	Peak Viscosity (Pv)	Trough Viscosity (Tv)	Breakdown (Pv-Tv)	Final Viscosity (Fv)	Setback (Fv - Pv)	Peak Time (min)	Pasting Temperature (°C)
NA	4624	3227	1397	4215	988	5.13	77.03
NI	4639	3668	971	4720	1052	5.77	79.05
OA	1848	1151	697	1334	183	5.13	77.43
OI	1850	1199	651	1398	199	5.20	77.85
AcA	2285	1739	546	1957	218	5.83	91.28
AcI	3657	2849	808	3458	609	5.83	84.40
ATA	608	605	3	608	3	2.43	-
ATI	607	601	6	604	3	4.30	-

The means are the triple determinations of the results.

NA: Native Acha Starch; NI: Native Iburu Starch; OA: Oxidised Acha Starch; AcA: Acetylated Acha Starch; ATA: Acid Thinned Acha Starch; OI: Oxidised Iburu Starch; AcI: Acetylated Iburu Starch; ATI: Acid Thinned Iburu Starch.

Received: 2 September 2024
Revised: 15 September 2024
Accepted: 24 September 2024
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4.0 Conclusion

Starches obtained from the two varieties were subjected to chemical modifications and physicochemical properties. The functional quality, selectivity, and appropriateness of modified starch for different industrial food, pharmaceutical, and nutritional formulations are influenced by its modification. The study's findings demonstrated that, among the two varieties; the seed grains of black fonio (*Digitaria iburua*) had a low moisture content, crude fat and crude fibre than white fonio (*Digitaria exilis*). This indicated that the former has a longer shelf life than the latter. Meanwhile, the modification processes employed resulted in reducing values of non-starchy substances (protein, lipids, moisture and fiber). This could probably be because the modified starches were prepared with further screening and washing. The reduction in non-starchy substances enable them to be important in some industrial uses, and their low protein content makes them beneficial in the creation of syrups that contain more glucose than native starches. The qualities of native starches are contrasted with chemically modified which indicated that process of acetylation increased swelling power and amylose content of both samples. Oxidation and acid thinning displayed much difference in the pasting properties which may be due to the granules of starch. These processes lessen the intensity of polymerisation of paste viscosity and starch content. Oil capacity was enhanced with oxidation but there was a decrease in acetylated and acid thinned starches, the comparatively elevated quantity of hydrophobic residues in both samples has the potential to be used as food coating and bioplastic sheets. The lower setback viscosities of the two varieties starches would enable them to be used to generate gels, which are desired in culinary products such as sauces thickened with starch. However, there was a slight variation in the physicochemical characteristics of iburu (*Digitaria iburua*) related to acha (*Digitaria exilis*); this difference can be attributed to morphological and/or genetic properties. The starch industry is always growing, and its adaptability is increased through modification methods, therefore, applications of starch modifications (physical and chemical) can be modified to suit various needs both in and outside of food sectors thereby increasing the demand for starch in industry.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

5.0 References

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